

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TYPICAL FEATURES OF THE STUDENT'S BECOMING A SUBJECT OF THE PROCESS OF THE LESSON MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The article explains the relevance of the topic. It emphasizes that the study of how to create a problem situation in the learning process is effective in theory and practice; the learning process relies on all cognitive processes; their unity and cognitive processing in students develop purposefully in the learning process.

It recalls that thinking is necessary only where there are new goals, when the learned methods and means of action (although they are essential) are few, and such conditions are an example of a problem situation. Besides, the article provides the scientific and pedagogical explanations of the goals of creating cognitive needs through a problem situation, the reasons for the problem situation, the problem-solving process, the functions performed by the subjects of this activity, and the lawfulness and naturalness of the problem situation in the educational process.

In this work, presented as a research paper, there is the following generalization: the independent acquisition of new knowledge and methods by students in a learning system formed by the level of development of pedagogical thought and practice does not occur outside the 'learning problem' solution; the emergence of a problem situation in this system is only the beginning of the mental activity.

Keywords: cognitive need; problem situation; a perceived difficulty; the degree of the complexity of the problem; a central question; perception from above and below; purposefully created problem situation; a cognitive issue; the basis of the solution.

The relevance of the research

It is clear that a large part of the teacher's activity, which is the main "opportunity component" of the learning process, is to formulate and solve didactic cognitive problems related to the realization of continuous mental activities aimed at the expected results of students. It is undeniable that continuing mental activity occurs when there is a perceived object that can meet the needs of its subject; in other words, the purpose of the subject of the action in question is conditioned by the need to assimilate that fact. When the goal-action model being confronted by the learner in the learning process is formed in the form of a problem, the situation is conditioned by understanding the mismatch between the level of availability of opportunities and the need for its solution, which begins the continuous mental activity. The study of how this beginning occurs in the learning process is theoretically and technologically essential, and the directions of this research depend on the formation of the teaching system and the level of development of the educational field adequate to the challenges of the industrial revolutions (now the IV industrial revolution), in other words, the problem of the research in this area is everlasting.

The interpretation of research materials

Each research project begins with identifying the problem. The real problem always gives rise to many hypotheses and assumptions, and to test them it is first necessary to formulate a research question because the research question serves as a guide in learning new knowledge. It is also possible to transfer this reasoning to a perfect learning system, and this stage is also named motivation because it encourages students to think and be cognitively active.

Firstly, it is necessary to clarify what we mean by "perfect training system". Naturally, the level of development of pedagogical thought in each generation determines the level of successful training and development of its theoretical foundations, and this process is constantly improving. We consider the current level of development of pedagogical thought and pedagogical practice (or rather, the level we understand this treasure) to be adequate to the educational field being formed with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution, constructivism that will lead to the development of thinking, cooperative learning aimed at the social development of students; creating conditions for the independent acquisition of knowledge and skills, adherent

to the principles of the teacher acting as an organizational coordinator, in some cases as an arbitrator, embracing problematic, algorithmic, programming, differentiation and other approaches as its subsystems, the emergence of action with the paradigm "opportunity-action-new quality" and evaluate the perfection of the system at the desired level of development.

As it is known, one of the main concepts related to the learning process is the problem situation, it is a means of activating the mental activity of the student and managing the process of acquiring new knowledge, so the study of how to create a problem situation in the learning process is effective in theory and practice. [1; 334]

It is clear from the methodological, psychological, and didactic bases of the perfect learning system that it relies on all cognitive processes; their unity, and the cognitive processes in the learners that develop in the learning process. As a result, "... training should lead to the development of student's generalized cognitive abilities. Otherwise, the learner will not be able to solve this or that problem in life on his own If the subjects of learning have general methods of thinking in solving problems, they can apply these generalized cognitive techniques to each new problem." [2; 24]

It is also clear that thinking needs to be where there are new goals, where the old, previous methods and means of action (although they are necessary) are lacking. Such a situation is an example of a problem situation. As shown in the textbook "General Psychology", "... thinking is the search and discovery of the new. Where it is possible to move with old, already known methods of operation with previous knowledge and habits, there is no problem situation and, of course, there is no need for active thinking. [9; 344]

A well-known psychologist, S.L. Rubinstein also wrote that the starting point of the thought process is a problematic situation. As a result, "... when a person needs to understand something, he begins to think. Thinking often begins with a problem and a question, a surprise and a wonder. Through this problematic situation, the individual participates in the process of thinking, he is always lead to the solution of any problem ... "[15; 347]. The emergence of problems in various fields of science is not accidental and is related to the so-called "problem situation" [12, 25]. Based on this situation lies the dialectical contradiction; i.e., a problem situation is a contradiction between the knowledge of the requirements of individuals' practical and theoretical activities and the ignorance of the ways, methods, and techniques of carrying out these activities. [14; 131]

Unlike scientific research, a problem situation in the learning process arises from the need to perform learning tasks, where what is necessary for the theoretical or practical implementation of the task, belongs directly to the immediate developmental zone of the student. The mental state of the learner in this process characterizes the problem situation.

The starting point of the learner's intellectual activity, which aims at meeting the need to define something new for the task, is directly related to the problem

situation. A.M. Matyushkin writes that the problem situation is, first, not a learning task; it is characterized by the mental state of the learner, and it occurs during the learning task [11; 100]. Concerning this issue, A. Nurushov also notes that the solution to the problem situation is a perceived difficulty that demands a search. A problem situation arises only when the hardness is perceived, that is when the learner can accept it as the solution. [7; 69]

From our point of view, there are the following three goals in creating a cognitive need through a problem situation, which is realized by meeting that need: 1) to learn to acquire new knowledge, as well as to apply the acquired knowledge in a new, unfamiliar situation, 2) qualitative learning of knowledge in the conditions of creative application, 3) to prepare the subject of learning to independently apply the methods of science appropriate to the age and level of knowledge.

It should take no notice that the problem that arises because of the analysis of the problem situation is a psychological-didactic category, and the issue, which acts as a psychological-didactic category, contains new knowledge, new ways of learning that (both process and outcome) determines the structure of the process (intellectual activity). [8; 5] The problem is a transition from old information to a new one by resolving relevant contradictions [6; 98]. Taking this into account, philosophers and psychologists rightly point out that the problem-solving process can be determined as the result of a contradiction between past theoretical knowledge and new facts that cannot be explained on their basis. Of course, there are some peculiarities to problem-solving defined by the learning process. For example, in the learning process, it is important to remember that the problem can be posed by the learner and the teacher. It should take no notice that any training material being new to the learner has contradictions and that this material can be a problem for him under certain conditions. Some of them also depend on the form of presentation of the training material to the learner.

The problem situation does not arise in the learning process in any case. When the learning material forms specially, the learner can see that the new information does not correspond to his previous experience (if his goal is to understand, he can not achieve this goal).

It is clear that the optimal formulation of the problem, creating the question is not an immediate and direct process. There are two phases in the process of a problem statement: 1) "seeing" the problem, revealing it; 2) the problem question itself.

In this process, the following questions arise in a somewhat complicated way:

1. General indefinite form representing only one side of the initial conflict;
2. Putting the question in concrete form (reflecting both sides of the initial contradiction);
3. Specific qualitative form of the question (qualitative development of both sides of the initial contradiction and localization of the search area of the answer).

The philosophical literature also shows that any problem consists of a central question and questions

grouped around it. Before the main question is formulated, there are questions and additional questions. The first describes finding the problem, and the second characterizes solving the problem.

In the learning process, the problem is posed by both the teacher and the learner, and both have appropriate goals. Several basic logical acts must be expected in the formulation of the training problem. These are mainly:

First, the teacher must not forget that knowledge that is directly related to the material to be taught and used to master solving the problem cannot be challenged without updating the previously acquired knowledge group;

Second, based on the specifics of the training, the teacher must know the level of preparation of their students.

According to these logical acts, there are the following rules before posing a problem: The first rule is to differentiate between known and unknown knowledge related to the actualization of previous knowledge and action methods.

In the second case, known and unknown are localized. From this, it is clear that, first, the teacher cannot pose any problem to the learner; he must only pose a problem that the learner can accept as his problem. Second, the learner must learn the localization techniques of the unknown, distinguishing it from all other non-essential elements.

There is a need for a third rule, which determines the possible conditions for an independent solution. As a result, it is necessary to define the type of problem and its solution. Both the teacher and the learner must be able to do this. Define the type of problem by the teacher is because he a) puts it correctly; b) chooses a rational option for its solution, and c) identifies ways to manage students' activities to solve the problem independently. The learner must identify the type of problem to find ways and means to solve it more quickly and rationally.

Finally, the fourth rule is uncertainty in the formulation of the problem. [10; 355-361]

In scientific sources, it is often possible to come across two more concepts: the emergence of a problem situation and the creation of a problem situation.

M. Kruglyak believes it is incorrect to say that "the teacher creates a problematic situation", the situation itself being objective [3; 134]. It can be stated that, first, "problem situation" and "problem" are psychological phenomena and are based on an objective, dialectical contradiction.

Second, if a problem situation arises from the point of view of learning the problem concerning the subject position, the teacher himself creates it because of the application of special methodological approaches from the point of view of problem teaching. As a result, it is expedient to consider creating a problem situation as a "pedagogical concept and a means of organizing training."

There is always a problem for the learning subjects in mastering the subject to be studied (as a manifesta-

tion of dialectical contradictions inherent in any concept). This is a natural situation until the learner has fully mastered the learning material.

The emergence of a problematic situation, regardless of the teacher, is a natural phenomenon in the educational process. It probably activates mental activity, but this activation is not systematic; it cannot be "the result of the use of scientifically substantiated pedagogical influences on the individual."

There is no doubt that the methodologically correct definition of the methods of creating a problem situation occurs when the teacher is aware of the regularities of its occurrence. In the relevant literature (especially about problem-based learning), it makes sense to identify the types of problem situations - there are attempts to formulate these patterns.

Research in learning psychology has shown that different types of problem situations create various conditions for thinking. A teacher's knowledge of the main types of problem situations helps to identify ways to form such situations and manage students' cognitive activity. Prof. M. A. Hamzayev writes that A. M. Matyushkin noted that there are two main types of problem situations in the learning process. According to him, the same problem can be posed both theoretically and practically. [3; 135]

The first type of problem situation arises concerning the presentation of a theoretical problem based on some general facts already known to the learner. In the psychological literature, this path is called "perception from above" (N.A. Menchinskaya). This type of problem aims at discovering the facts that learners need to acquire, master, or understand, to understand new information or justify new work in a situation.

The second type of problem situation manifested itself in the training process is related to the practical problem. The essence of such a problem situation is that the subjects of learning need to overcome several "intellectual barriers" that they face to do the work known to them. This path is called the "bottom-up" path in psychological literature. (N.A. Menchinskaya). In this case, it is necessary to find a solution to the current situation.

The classification of problem situations in the learning process, and their types are the subject of extensive discussion. For example, TV Kudryavtsev identified six types of problem situations. These are:

1) The problem situation arises when there is a discrepancy between the existing system of knowledge of learning subjects (learners) and the requirements of the topic;

2) The possibility of a problematic situation arises when the subjects with a learning function are required to choose a system that provides the correct solution to the problem from the various existing knowledge systems;

3) The problem situation arises when learners are required to use the acquired knowledge in new practical conditions;

4) The problem situation arises when the practical application of the method chosen by the theoretical solution of the problem or the theoretical substantiation of the result obtained practically does not correspond;

5) The problem situation arises when the constructive design of the concrete technical installation does not match the appearance of the schematic technical drawings;

6) A problematic situation can arise when the static nature of many schematic representations requires them to be based on the dynamism of spatial images while reading. [10; 368-369]

As can be seen, TV Kudryavtsev, in determining the types of problem situations encountered by the learning parties (subjects) in the learning process, considers various types of contradictions between knowledge and ignorance and is generally correct. The types of problem situations mentioned in the list include the typology of the Polish didactic G. Navatsky. However, two of the types shown by TV Kudryavtsev (second and sixth in numbering) are not in the typology of G. Navatsky. [3; 136]

We can divide the problem situation manifested itself in the learning process into two groups according to its emergence purposefully (using scientifically based and systematic use of specific methods and tools) or independently of the teacher.

There are several goals in purposeful problem situations. We can distinguish the following two of them:

1. Creating a problem situation to direct the learning subject to the set goal, promoting learning;
2. Creation of a purposeful problem situation, which includes the problem formulation and the acquisition of new knowledge and methods of action with its solution.

As you know, a problem is explained by solving one or more problems. As a result, when creating a problem situation, the teacher takes as a basis a problem that he will formulate (or will be formulated by the learner) and the problem that consists of its solution. The solution to these issues means the acquisition of new knowledge and methods of action. As a result, such problem situations can merge into four groups:

1. Cognitive problem formulated problem situation in which its analysis and conditions are obvious, but the solution, the theoretical and practical basis on which the solution develops, and the result are unknown;
2. Cognitive problem formulated problem situation in which the analysis and condition, the basis on which the solution develops, and the result is unknown, but the solution is obvious;
3. Cognitive problem formulated problem situation in which the analysis and condition, the solution, and the result are unknown, but the basis of the solution is obvious;
4. Cognitive problem formulated problem situation in which the analysis and condition, the basis on which the solution develops, and the solution are unknown, but the result is obvious.

This division is more typical for additional education students.

The creation of a problematic situation aims at the following didactic purposes:

- 1) directs the learner's attention to the question, issue, or educational theme, and arouses cognitive interest in them;

2) such cognitive difficulties imposed on the learner lead to the continuation of the activity of their mental activities;

3) reveals to the subject of learning the contradiction between the need for cognition and the possibility of its fulfillment;

4) supports the learners focusing on the cognitive problem, question, the main problem in the task, and the search for a way out of the difficulty;

5) helps the learner define the boundaries of previous knowledge that needs to be updated and guides the search for a more rational way out of difficulty.

M. I. Mahmutov identified the following eight main ways to create a problem situation:

1) to motivate students to explain life events and facts theoretically;

2) use of life and learning situations arising within implementing practical tasks;

3) setting research tasks for students as creating a problem situation;

4) to motivate students to the analysis of facts and events, to compare them with the logical contradictions of scientific concepts with life ideas about these tactics;

5) organization of research and hypothesis to create a problem situation;

6) to motivate students to compare, contrast, and put together facts, events, rules, and activities;

7) to motivate students to initial generalization of new facts;

8) to acquaint students with the setting of scientific problems in the history of science development. [10; 368-369]

It is commendable in M. Makhmutov's opinion that his methods determine the following three types of dialectical contradictions: a) the contradiction between the need for understanding new and the impossibility of this understanding with the previous learning, b) the contradiction between new facts and the previously learned knowledge c) the contradiction between the life experience of the learners and objective knowledge.

As we have mentioned, the emergence of a problem situation is only the beginning of the mental activity. Independent acquisition of new knowledge and action methods can not be done without an independent solution to the problem. The organization and management of this process are connected with two main regularities. The first regularity is psychological (the level of difficulty of learning), and the second regularity is psycholinguistic (the connection of the verbal expression of the problem with the direction of the decisive thought).

The sequence of operations in solving a problem is, in fact, a step of mastery, as each of them leads the student to solve the problem completely.

The analysis of the problem situation is the first stage of the student's independent cognitive activity. Attempts to get out of a difficult situation are associated with the student's mental activity, which aims at identifying the elements of the situation that cause the difficulty. The activity begins with asking questions: What is given? What is unknown? What do you need to know?

Understanding the relationship between the known knowledge of the learner and the new facts and events that create the problem situation is the essential condition for the correct formulation of the problem.

The problem situation often arises because of the teacher's formulating the problem. In this case, the learner begins to analyze the problem itself and seeks a solution. In setting the learning problem, he applies many logical operations (mainly the methods of comparison and analogy).

The problem-solving process begins when the student: a) formulates the problem himself or b) accepts the teacher's formulation and independently seeks solutions to the problem.

Of course, the formulation of the problem by the teacher and the learner to a large extent depends on the complexity of the problem and the depth of its content. Often, the form of problem expression differs not only between the teacher and the learner but also between individual learners. Depending on the accuracy of expressing the problem, its solution is successful.

Thus, the problem arises in the head of the learner because of a complete analysis of the situation, depending on the separation of known and unknown information. The problem statement begins with problem-solving. The solution itself is a stage of educational-cognitive activity, which is considered one of the complex elements of problem-based learning and consists of several sub-stages and rings.

The didactic arsenal contains a wealth of practical experience in solving didactic requirements and content problems, and psychologists have identified the logic of problem-solving. Indeed, the concrete regularity of the creative solution of the problem has not been formed to the end, but some results have been obtained in the research of psychologists. Unfortunately, the theory of the gradual formation of mental activity of P.Y. Galperin has not been used sufficiently in didactics for organizing more effective methods of the mental activity of the pupil, student, and participant in solving problematic issues.[3; 139]

By the way, D. Poya's work in the field of research on the principles and ways of solving problems attracts attention. In the book "How to solve a task" D. Poya gave a scheme for solving mathematical problems. The scheme shows the sequence of intellectual activities necessary for success. It covers four stages: a) understanding the problem; b) drawing up a solution plan; c) implementing the plan, and d) looking back (analysis of the result obtained). [13; 13-16]

The main issue in implementing these stages is to answer the following questions: What is known? What is given? What are the conditions? Is the condition good enough to find the unknown? Have I encountered such an issue? Can't its solution methods and techniques be used here? And so on. By the way, the concept of "problem" is not only related to the teaching of mathematics; it is essential to take advantage of applying cognitive problems in teaching all subjects. Even a teacher can look at the process used in his lesson as a matter of didactic cognition, and if he successfully implements this approach, his effectiveness will increase. Many years of our experience guide us to this conclusion.

The scientific novelty of the research

The theoretical and experimental aspects of creating a problem situation were clarified in the process of adequate learning for the emerging educational field.

The theoretical significance of the research

The considerations on creating a problem situation in the process of adequate learning for the emerging educational space have been generalized based on a "system-structural" dialectical approach.

The experimental significance of the research

It is believed that the novelty of the experimentation has a positive effect on the formation of an environment in which the theoretical and practical aspects of the problem situation arise (or create) in the experimental activity of the educator, who must perform the "opportunity function" as a central component in the learning process.

The result

1) One of the main concepts of adequate training for the emerging educational space is the problem situation; 2) The problem situation is one of the means of activating the mental activity of the subject, learning in the training system, and managing the process of knowledge acquisition; 3) The study of how a problem situation arises in the learning process is theoretically and practically useful, as research in this area is of an everlasting nature.

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USING GOOGLE SERVICES TO TEACH ENGLISH

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Abstract

At present, new information technologies and telecommunication means have been widely used not only in scientific research and management of various social, economic and political processes, but also in the education system. The range of new forms of education using information technologies and computer networks is expanding. The rise of society to a new level, its driving force is the comprehension and application of experience and the past in the education of young people in accordance with the requirements of modern times. One of these needs is to increase cognitive activity through Internet sources. This requires a full quality of knowledge on the productive implementation of the problem and the formation of skills and abilities to use it in the practice of students. The main purpose of teaching English is the formation and development of students' communicative culture, practical training in mastering English.

Keywords: information technology, internet sources, English language, the education system.

As the political scientist T. Abduali noted: "we are very worried when the head of state raises the issue of globalization. Globalization is, simply put, the strengthening of our relations with countries that have reached a high level. One of them is language communication. To do this, it is necessary to inculcate young people to learn English, which is the language of international communication. We are acutely aware of its need over time." And Doctor of Philology, Professor, Academician of the International Academy of Pedagogical Sciences, teacher T. Tanirbergenovna continues her thought: "learning English, we do not waste time. English does not interfere with the study of the Kazakh language. We just need to understand. Because English does not compete with the state language."

Russian scientist E. M. Ryt assessed the foreign language: "the methodology of teaching a foreign language is a practical determinant of comparative linguistics." On the importance of including information technologies in the methodology of teaching a foreign language, scientist O. Tatarnikov expresses his opinion as follows: "there is evidence that a computer creates opportunities for the development of visual – imaginative thinking, motor and verbal communication skills, purposeful activity and socialization." Here, according to these scientists, you can see the importance of using information technology, the Internet when learning English and learning English. The XXI century is the era of the information society, the era of technological culture, the era of careful attitude to the outside world, human health, professional culture.

Informatization of the educational process involves improving the efficiency and quality of all levels

of the educational process, realizing the goals of developmental learning, personality-oriented learning using new information technologies.

In addition, the use of various didactic methods in information technology has its own rich history, deep content, diverse features. As you know, modernity requires the use of new technologies and active methods of spiritual, aesthetic, emotional, intellectual impact on students, the development of their personal and qualitative qualities. Because this is a guarantee of the quality of their work at school. Therefore, in the process of increasing the cognitive activity of students through Internet sources, it is necessary to introduce an increase in cognitive activity in the educational process of general educational institutions. It requires not only new information tools, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process [1].

The use of computer technologies significantly changes approaches to the development of educational material on the discipline in teaching foreign languages.

The use of Internet resources presupposes a new form of cognitive activity of students, the result of which is the formation of cognitive independence skills in students, the development of new knowledge in the field of search and orientation, replenishment and realization of knowledge independently.

The main purpose of teaching a foreign language is to develop the communicative culture of students and the skills of practical knowledge of a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to create favorable conditions for students to learn a foreign language. The Internet